

Introduction

At the start of the PARSEC project the Data Strand wanted to get an ‘entry profile’: a picture of current data activity of the team members and their experience with tools along the data lifecycle. In the case of a synthesis group, where re-use of existing data is the standard, some of the traditional research life cycle steps are missed (e.g. Michener, 2012), a simplified data lifecycle being more relevant (Figure 1).

In this project we wish to periodically review the status of:

- understanding and awareness of the wider data landscape, and
- use of tools both across the whole group (synthesis and data strands),

which will help us gauge group development.

This will enable us, at an individual level to:

- respond to needs, such as provide training opportunities, and
- most effectively capitalise on the skillsets in the group.

Figure 1: the synthesis data life cycle from Specht *et al.*, 2015.

A survey form was administered in hard copy at the October 2019 synthesis team meeting and emailed to other members who were not at the meeting. The last responses were received in June 2020 as new members joined the group. The survey questions did not directly refer to the steps in the data lifecycle but were guided by them. Nineteen responses were received from the 24 members of the synthesis team, with two additional responses from members of the data team who were present at the synthesis meeting in October. Their responses are not included in this report. These are small numbers, so caution should be applied to any conclusions you may draw. Please also note that no-one is identified by name in this report; a deliberate choice which must be respected.

Profile questions

1. Firstly we asked what proportion of time for research did people spend working with others.

On a scale of 1-10 where 1 was ‘no time’ and 10 is ‘all my time’, the responses were 7.08 ± 1.67 (mean and standard deviation). The group is quite collaborative.

2. We then asked the question whether the respondent worked mainly by themselves, in a small or large team, as a support to a research team, as a support to a work team, or in some other situation. More than one response was possible.

Respondents could select more than one option, and two respondents selected two. Twelve of the respondents said they worked in small teams, 43 in large teams, 2 supported research teams (including the CESAB director) and three respondents worked by themselves. When asked to comment, there was clearly variety in the working situation according to the project and role in the project. R1 said “2-5 people on specific tasks”, R4 said “variable: typically between 10-20 collaborators, sometimes as little as 3” and R15 qualified their selection of ‘large group’ by saying “large multi and inter-disciplinary groups”. R10 responded “I provide analytical/statistical support to a large variety of <snip> staff but, mainly work with a small science team across numerous projects. I also have my own research and collaborate with university partners and my own graduate students.”, while R11 said “I am a PI of lab. [The] research interest of students [are] little far from this project currently. R13 said “my research is conducted based on outputs of other people. Currently I am working with 2 persons (1 PI and 1 technical support)”. R15 has complicated responsibilities “Currently, I lead three research teams. I also collaborate on two other research teams. In addition, I have non-research activities that involve helping manage our strategies across the organization. This involves working with executive leaders and with business unit and strategy leaders across our organization and using and developing an internal reporting system”.

3. The respondents were then asked what type of data they worked on, where natural science data was characterised by either observational or experimental, and machine-generated data by meteorological or hydrological. More than one type of data could be identified.

The majority of respondents had experience working on observational data, with social and economic data and remote sensed and modelled data equally important (Figure 2). The majority of respondents worked on more than one type of data, with four working on two types of data, six on three types of data, and three working across four types of data (these four all worked on the following suite: observational data, remote-sensed data, modelled data and social and economic data). There was a fairly even spread in the clarifying comments between image processing within a geo-spatial context, and ecological-human dimension work.

“Biodiversity, environment, sociology” (R1); “it depends on the project I am working on” (R2); “computer science / signal processing localisation / identification of objects in image / video / 3D data...”(R3); “almost always within a geospatial context, or I will translate into geospatial” (R4); “image data (2D, 3D, video)” (R5); “theoretical ecology, biogeography, species distributions” (R6); “generally research is done on a combination of remote sensing data and ground truth data together with other types of data such as ecological or socio-economic” (R7); “Most of my work is dedicated to the production of environmental indicators of natural processes combining remotely-sensed data from satellites and *in situ* observation data” (R8); “In my role as a biometrician, I work with a large variety of data. However, much of it is spatial in nature or based on field data collection” (R10), “as a data scientist I feel free to work with any kind of data. On my previous projects, mainly experimental data from various multidisciplinary fields are transformed into networks” (R13); “ecological studies / wildlife, human dimensions (questionnaires)” (R14); “My team works with observational and experimental social and economic data (e.g. from focus groups, surveys, interviews, and randomized controlled trials), as well as remotely sensed “natural science data” data measuring the outcome (cover crops) of a behavioural economic experiment. In addition, my teams work with satellite images, land cover data, field survey data on vegetative communities, agricultural data, geographic or physical data (e.g., elevation), and reporting data on conservation management actions, intermediate results, and outcomes” (R15).; “I’m working with satellite images and consumption expenditures with the aim of reproduce works done in scientist literature. These works introduce methods to estimate consumption expenditures with satellite images” (R17); and, “My work goes through the entire data lifecycle, depending on projects. However, most of my work tends to be analysing and visualizing third-party data” (R19).

Figure 2: Types of data the subsample of the PARSEC participants worked on.

4. We asked whether people included Data Management Plans in their research projects.

Of the 19 respondents, 8 said they did include a DMP, 10 said they did not, and one person did not answer the question.

We then asked whether they (or someone in their team) updated the DMP during the project.

Of the 19 respondents, 5 people said they updated their DMP during their project, ten said they did not and four did not answer. Open comments provided the following:

“[I do the DMP] mostly at the end of the project” (R1); “if a database is created, it is put on a website” (R3); “depends on how complex the project is” (R4); “started to do so only 2 years ago” (R6); “we created several portals for data access (the DMP is linked to the portal, and covers access, licensing etc.)” (R7); “We’ve been trying to do that in our last projects, however we still encounter problems with the storage and sharing of data, especially satellite imagery with very large volumes of data, difficult to store and transfer to partners with limited resources” (R8); “I normally write a study plan for research projects but rarely modify them during the course of the research” (R10); “Basically all data should be Open we think but there are some problems mainly data storage spaces” (R11); “I’ve ignored this theme. In past days I’ve been getting more involved” (R13); “We have data management plans for some projects but not all” (R15); and, “I have been involved in projects requiring management plans but my work rarely fell under those plans” (R19).

5. We asked what proportion of time respondents spent in their most recent research projects finding data

On a scale of 1-10 where 1 was 'no time' and 10 is 'all my time', the responses were 4.37 ± 1.62 . Apparently not much time was spent on finding data. Four respondents made comments, which were: "depends on the project I am working on" (R2); "often it is the most time-consuming part" (R4); "Free satellite imagery is becoming a general trend. Finding it is pretty easy" (R8); "In our international work, I spend a considerable amount of time finding suitable data" (R10); "this was one of our big problems. We were implementing AI tools, but we were lacking enough data to do any training" (R13); "My projects often requiring finding data but I personally rarely do it (vs technical staff)" (R19).

6. We asked what proportion of their time in their most recent research projects did they spend on cleaning, matching and blending (harmonising) data.

On a scale of 1-10 where 1 was 'no time' and 10 is 'all my time', the responses were 4.55 ± 2.41 . The responses ranged from 10 (one respondent), through 7 (three respondents) to 1 (two). The nine comments offered suggest that several respondents either worked with machine-generated data with fairly standard formats, or have assistants to help with this phase, but some were really 'getting their hands dirty': "I ask someone else to do it" (R2); "we often work on benchmark databases" (R3); "often iterative with finding data" (R4); "not a major problem with remote sensed data" (R8). A response from someone who had scored '7' for effort: "This is a very time-consuming portion of any analysis but, with data from numerous sources, quality checking, formatting and synthesizing data, is a notable challenge" (R10); "my research work consists of designing data cleaning methods" (R12); "Since I've worked mainly with network data, many repositories have different formats of data, different types of reading. Also, these data includes isolated nodes, so we have to compute a cleaning algorithm (which depends on the implementation, so the output may vary from user to user)" (R13); "In a recent project, this has taken half or more of the time and merging datasets has created serious barriers" (R15); "I personally rarely do it (vs technical staff)" (R19).

7. The group was asked whether they had aligned their data elements with a standardised vocabulary.

Fewer people said they used a standardised vocabulary than not (7 to 12), and comments were: "ISO categories" (R4); "as much as possible (R6); "we used classification systems like LCCS and ontologies" (R7); "We have to respect standards when "using remote sensing data (OGC standards) and creating products from images (metadata formats especially)" (R8); "My speciality is biodiversity science so I can use Darwin Core terms" (R11); "In my last work, I've implemented an algorithm to parse different data to a standard data, a plain format very commonly known in my field. The names and codes for the elements are well known in computer sciences area" (R13); "when possible" (R14). One respondent stated they did not really understand the question.

8. Question 7 was followed by asking whether respondents used any metadata standards in the description of their data or data products.

The respondents were invited to indicate whether they used standards and if they did, use a controlled vocabulary of: DwC (Darwin Core); EML; FGDC; XML Observations and Measurements; DataCite Schema; ISO; OGIS; Metadata standardized within my institution, lab, or project; None; and Other (please specify).

Ten of the 19 respondents said they used metadata standards, while 9 said they did not.

A wide range of metadata standards is currently being used (Figure 3), not all singly. One member reported using five standards (including metadata standardised in the institution, lab or project), one using four and one using three, and four using two standards. Those who clicked 'other' did not use any of the standards offered and said they used CIDOC CRM or OGC.

Figure 3: Metadata standards the subsample of the PARSEC participants had used. No-one in the group used DataCite Schema.

9. We then asked what proportion of time in their most recent research projects did they spend analysing data.

On a scale of 1-10 where 1 was 'no time' and 10 is 'all my time', the responses were 5.34 ± 2.58 . Responses ranged from 1 to 10 on the 10 point scale.

The open responses were few: "It depends on the project I am working on" (R2); "analysing data = developing new algorithms to analyse data" (R5); "my students spend most of their time" (R14); "this is most of my work but typically done in practice by graduate students" (R19).

10. We asked whether people recorded their work using a workflow system.

Of the 19 respondents, ten said they used a workflow system, eight said they did not and one did not answer. Of those that said 'yes' respondents were invited to select from a list of workflow systems including Hydrant; Kepler; myExperiment; R Markdown (RMD); Jupyter notebook; Pegasus; Science Pipes; Taverna; Other. More than one selection could be made.

Figure 4: Workflow systems used by the respondents.

Only two of the listed workflow systems were identified (Figure 4) with some other options identified. A miscellaneous series of comments arose for 'other': "we write everything in a text file and then report the protocol on the associated document" (R3); "model builder in spatial systems (ArcGIS)" (R4); "use text file...to 'archive' the procedure" (R5); "I usually write tutorials on the methods I use in order to share it with colleagues, students and partners" (R8); "researchers on my teams use different systems" (R15); and, "on paper (notebook)" (R19).

11. We asked whether team members had ever published their data.

A small majority of respondents (13 out of the 19 respondents) said they had published their data. Six said they had not. If they had published their data, we asked how much time they spent on the publication process, on a scale of 1-10 where 1 was 'no time' and 10 is 'all my time', the responses were 3.73 ± 2.14 .

We then asked in an open-ended question, "if you answered 'yes' <snip> how you chose the repository for your data". This elicited the most responses of all the questions with nearly everyone adding a comment. "Easiest and cheapest" (R1); "website" (R3); "Data.gov via Landscape Approach portal w/BLM through the Alaska Center for Conservation Science: accs.uaa.alaska.edu" (R4); "web page of laboratory" (R5); "dryad or Zenodo" (R6); "we created our own repository" (R7); "The repository is chosen in accordance with the infrastructure and storage capacity provided by my lab" (R8); "Dryad if fees covered by the journal. Otherwise figshare" (R9); "I commonly go with journal repositories but, we have frequently utilized cloud-based service (e.g., AWS S3) and Java based webmap services to make data and published analysis results available" (R10); "In my field we can deposit our data in the GBIF and LTER data bases so there is small difficulty. There are already sophisticated tools and methods" (R11); "This is another issue. We published the data into our local server, however, sometimes it is off" (R13); "as data paper only" (R14); "I have published data as part of the supplement to a paper" (R15). A telling comment was "I actually have data I would have liked to publish but never spent the time to understand how it should be done..." (R19).

12. A final question presented options used by Tenopir et al. in their surveys (e.g. 2011, 2015 and 2020). How do you expect data providers (including you) might want to be credited?

Group members were asked to respond with a simple 'yes' or 'no' and 'did not answer' (dna)

option	Yes	No	dna
1. co-authorship on publications resulting from use of the data.	5	14	0
2. acknowledgement of the data providers in all disseminated work making use of the data.	17	2	0
3. citation of the data providers in all disseminated work making use of the data.	19	0	0
4. results based (at least in part) on the data could not be disseminated in any format without the data provider's approval.	3	15	1

5. results based (at least in part) on the data could not be disseminated without the data provider having the opportunity to review the results and make suggestions or comments, but approval not required.	4	15	0
6. reprints of articles that make use of the data must be provided to the data provider.	11	8	0
7. the data provider is given a complete list of all products that make use of the data, including articles, presentations, educational materials, etc.	6	13	0
8. legal permission for data use is obtained.	13	6	0
9. the data provider is given and agrees to a statement of uses to which the data will be put	14	5	0

Option numbers 2 and 3 (citation or acknowledgement of the data providers in all disseminated work making use of the data) was clearly favoured by all. Option number 1 was met by a comment “depending on the level of use of the data: yes OR no”. The most resounding negatives were options number 4 and 5 (results based (at least in part) on the data could not be disseminated without the data provider having the opportunity to review the results and make suggestions or comments, but approval not required) and to a lesser extent option 7. It will be interesting to see how flexible this type of provenance acknowledgement remains through the project, and also as options for quality assurance and crediting develop in the wider landscape. These responses and others are worth comparing with data partly reported in Tenopir et al. (2020) (Figure 5). Alignment is similar, but there are some interesting differences. Whether they are statistical or not is another question!

Figure 5: Responses by the PARSEC synthesis team (left) to a series of questions about conditions of data sharing, replicated from those asked by Tenopir et al. in 2011, 2015 and 2020. On the right are the responses reported in Tenopir et al., 2020 obtained from an average of 1,771.5 responses to each question from respondents from around the world. *at least in part.

References

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